

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

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ABSTRACT

The widespread use of antimicrobials in poultry production for therapeutic and non-therapeutic purposes has resulted in the emergence and dissemination of multidrug-resistant (MDR) Enterobacteriaceae, such as *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, *Proteus spp.*, and *Salmonella spp.* These organisms, routinely found in poultry and their environments, carry a variety of resistance genes that can be transferred to humans through the food chain, environmental contamination, and direct contact. The consequences of these resistance genes are profound, leading to increased morbidity and mortality associated with resistant infections. As a result, the effectiveness of last-resort antibiotics is compromised, resulting in the need for more expensive and less effective treatments, posing a substantial economic burden on healthcare systems. In this review, we discuss the resistance genes present in poultry and its environment, modes of transmission and acquisition of these resistance genes, and associated public health implications. It emphasizes the need for enhanced surveillance, alternative management strategies in poultry farming, and coordinated global efforts to mitigate the public health threat posed by resistant Enterobacteriaceae.

KEYWORDS: Enterobacteriaceae, resistance genes, poultry, antimicrobial resistance,

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INTRODUCTION

The discovery, commercialization, and extensive application of antimicrobial agents for the treatment of infections have revolutionized modern medicine and altered the therapeutic landscape [1]. Nonetheless, microorganisms have developed resistance against these antimicrobials. Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) is amongst the top ten global public health threats and development problem. According to the World Health Organisation (WHO) [2], monitoring antimicrobial resistance in commensal bacteria from food-producing animals is one of the top goals for WHO and the European Commission to better manage the transfer of antimicrobial resistance from food animal products to humans through the food chain.

Antimicrobials such as antibiotics have become vital for the advancement of effective medical practices, including

innovative surgical techniques, organ transplants, and the management of cancer patients. However, the rapid increase in resistance among common bacterial infections threatens this achievement, jeopardizing the recovery prospects of critically ill individuals. Consequently, bacterial resistance to antibiotics stands as one of the most pressing epidemiological challenges globally [3].

The widespread use of the same antibiotics in human and veterinary medicine, frequently without laboratory verification of the organism's susceptibility to antibiotics, has contributed to the development of resistant bacteria in humans and animals, as well as their spread in the environment [4]. The increasing resistance leads to serious consequences for both human and animal health. Studies have shown that in 2019, there were an estimated 4.5 million deaths globally associated with antibiotic resistance and 1.27

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

million deaths caused by antibiotic resistance, and this may rise significantly in the coming decades. The Western sub-Saharan Africa region had the highest number of deaths caused by antibiotic resistance (27.3 deaths per 100,000) [5]. Enterobacteriaceae are major contributors to the rise in antibiotic resistance, with significant morbidity and mortality linked to infections caused by resistant strains [5]. Enterobacteriaceae are gram-negative motile rods, non-spore-forming, non-acid-fast staining microorganisms that can grow within the temperature range of 22–350°C in the presence or absence of oxygen on MacConkey agar [6]. Most of them are catalase positive (except for *Plesiomonas* and *Shigella dysenteriae* O group 1), oxidase negative (except for *Plesiomonas*), and some can turn nitrate into nitrite (except for *Saccharobacter fermentatus* and some strains of *Erwinia* and *Yersinia*). All species react with glucose, forming acid and/or visible gas [6].

The impermeable and strengthened outer membrane of Enterobacteriaceae, unique to the family, contains the Enterobacteriaceae Common Antigen (ECA). The ECA is vital for the interaction between the bacteria and the environment and is pivotal for bacterial resistance. There are three main types of ECA: ECAPG, ECALPS, and ECACYC. The first two are located on the cell surface, while the third is located in the periplasm [7]. The outer membrane not only carries ECA but also carries other antigens used for the serological identification of bacteria. There are H (flagella), O (somatic), and K (capsular), which are useful for the motility of the organisms, protection, and interactions with the hostile environment [7].

They are widely present as commensals in nature and the environment [8] and they have several economic implications for humans and animals. Some of them are pathogenic and zoonotic, such as *Salmonella species*, which cause disease in humans, poultry, pigs, cows, and dogs, and *Escherichia coli*, which are responsible for diarrhoea in humans, lambs, piglets, and calves [6]. The *Klebsiella* and *Proteus species* are opportunistic pathogens. They cause a wide range of infectious diseases, such as urinary tract infections, pneumonia, liver abscesses, meningitis, and kidney stones [9,10].

Generally, the family is responsible for causing many diseases in humans, animals, and plants. Researchers have demonstrated that members of the Enterobacteriaceae family harbour resistant genes, whether they are commensal, pathogenic, opportunistic, or zoonotic. They are adapted to sharing genetic material, and more importantly, resistance is due to the 'mobile' transfer of resistance gene [11]. Because there are many plasmid-borne resistance genes and a lot of room for mutation when antibiotics are present, many members of this family are clinically important pathogens that can evade drugs. Furthermore, because of the lack of new treatments and the combination of different resistance mechanisms, Enterobacteriaceae have become a major threat to public health [12].

They get around antibiotics by changing how antibiotics work, creating resistant genes, changing target molecules, breaking down antibiotics using enzymes, and moving antimicrobials out of the cytosol [13]. All these mechanisms lead to antimicrobial resistance, which was initially a problem for the health sector and institutions but has since developed into a global issue [13]. For the average hospital practitioner in the late twentieth century, choosing therapy for severe infections caused by Enterobacteriaceae was simple. Recently, the antibiotic resistance of Enterobacteriaceae has developed so much that it is affecting the ability of the average clinician to make confident, trustworthy decisions [14].

Enterobacteriaceae are common commensals found in poultry and their environment. In a typical urban setting the poultry environment and their workers serve as a perfect interface between human and birds. The birds are considered one of the main reservoirs and sources of contamination to the public with organisms containing antimicrobial-resistant genes [15]. Multiple resistant genes, present in some of these organisms, confer multidrug and pandrug resistance. In this review, we will look at the different resistance genes present in some of these commensal and pathogenic Enterobacteriaceae, which are present in the poultry industry and humans, the mode of resistant gene transfer, and the public health implications of these circulating genes.

ENTEROBACTERIACEA AS RESERVOIRS OF RESISTANCE GENES

Microorganisms have developed resistance genes to all commonly used antibiotics, and resistant organisms are becoming increasingly prevalent [16]. Because they have more structural changes and antibiotic-breaking enzymes like expanded spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL), AmpC cephalosporinases, and carbapenemases, gram-negative bacteria are the most resistant to a wide range of drugs, especially Enterobacteriaceae producing carbapenemase [17]. ESBL and AmpC-producing bacteria are the primary targets of carbapenem antibiotics [18]. Carbapenem antibiotics are considered the final treatment option for bacterial infections [19].

The proliferation of Enterobacteriaceae makes them resistant to third-generation cephalosporins [20]. Third-generation cephalosporins (3GCs) are critical antimicrobial agents in the defence against gram-negative bacterial infections. It is usually faecal Enterobacteriaceae, like *Enterobacter spp.*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella spp.*, that make ESBLs, AmpC-lactamases, and carbapenemases 3GCs less effective [21]. Faecal Enterobacteriaceae, including *Enterobacter spp.*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Klebsiella spp.*, are commonly found in the human gastrointestinal tract, poultry gastrointestinal tract, and poultry environment [22].

A study carried out in Ghana to investigate the presence of ESBL in *E. coli* and *Klebsiella spp.* in poultry found that about 36% of the isolates produced ESBL, with most of them

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

containing the *bla*_{CTX-M-15} gene [23]. Animals, foods, and the environment have all been discovered to contain MDR-ESBL (multi-drug resistance and extended-spectrum-lactamase). These bacteria also exhibit resistance to carbapenems and β -lactam antibiotics [24].

Klebsiella spp. exhibits the most common AMR genes. The most commonly found AMR genes in human isolates are *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and *bla*_{OXA-48} [25]. Researchers have demonstrated that *Proteus spp.* can also generate ESBLs, AmpC cephalosporinases, and carbapenemases [25]. Studies have shown that some species of *Salmonella*, particularly *Salmonella* Kentucky, carry ESBL containing the *bla*_{CTX-M-14b} gene. Additionally, animal manure or faecal-contaminated surface water used for irrigation may introduce these bacteria into agricultural land [10].

Kluyvera, *Serratia*, and *Rahnella* species, which have soil and water as their major habitat, are natural carriers of ESBL genes and a source of 3GC-resistance determinants in the environment [21,26]. Due to the presence of multiple resistance genes on transferrable genetic elements like plasmids, transposons, or intergenic regions, ESBL-producing organisms are typically resistant to other antimicrobial agents like aminoglycosides, tetracyclines, chloramphenicol, trimethoprim, sulfonamides, or quinolones and therefore have multiple resistant genes [27].

This was confirmed by studies carried out by [12], who did an investigation on Enterobacteriaceae carriage in poultry in the West region of Cameroon and discovered that most of the ESBL-producing organisms were multi-drug resistant with multiple resistant genes found in them. In their study, they also discovered ESBL producers had the following genes: the *bla*_{TEM-1}, *bla*_{TEM-1}, *bla*_{TEM-2}, *bla*_{CTX-M}, *bla*_{SHV-1}, and *bla*_{KPC} gene. A study carried out in Portugal to investigate antibiotic resistance profiles in poultry and humans discovered that the isolates that were resistant to aminoglycosides, sulfonamides, trimethoprim, tetracyclines, chloramphenicol, or quinolones had ESBL-producing genes such as *bla*_{TEM-52}, *bla*_{SHV-2}, *bla*_{SHV-12}, and *bla*_{CTX-M-1} belonging to *E. coli*, *Klebsiella spp.*, and *Citrobacter spp.* About 67% of the isolates containing genes encoding ESBL were transferred among the species in conjugation experiments and have been seen in clinical isolates from Portuguese hospitals [28]. Also, [29] revealed that some of the ESBL-producing gene *bla*_{CTX-M-15} from poultry had a similar origin to that from humans. In addition to ESBLs, most Enterobacteriaceae are now developing resistance to most broad-spectrum antibiotics. Broad-spectrum β -lactam antibiotics like carbapenems are extremely important in human and animal medicine as they are regarded as the last resort treatment for gram-negative bacteria that are resistant to many drugs [24].

However, the rise of carbapenem-resistant bacteria poses a global danger to the effectiveness of carbapenems [30]. Ambler class A beta-lactamase (KPC), class B (metallo-enzymes), class D (OXA-48 type), and carbapenemase NDM-1 (New Delhi metallo-beta-lactamase-1) are the main

types of carbapenemases [30]. Researchers have identified ARGs like *mcr-1* and *tet X3* in poultry, their surroundings, and poultry workers, demonstrating a significant difference from those observed in individuals unrelated to poultry [15]. In the same study, [15] identified *mcr-10* in both human gut microbiomes and poultry gut. In a scientific report by [32], all the examined bacterial isolates that were resistant had resistance genes such as fluoroquinolones (*qnrA*, *qnrB*, *qnrS*), aminoglycosides (*strA-strB*, *aphA1*, *aac(3)-II*), sulfonamides (*sul1*, *sul2*, *sul3*), trimethoprim (*dfr1*, *dfr5*, *dfr7/17*), and tetracyclines (*tetA*, *tetB*).

Leinyuy found the following quinolone-resistant genes in their study on Enterobacteriaceae in poultry carriage: *qnrA*, *qnrS*, *qnrB* *aac(6)-IB-CR*, and *qepA* [12]. In a study carried out in Shandong, China, *P. mirabilis* isolates from poultry were multi-drug resistant and harboured several drug-resistance genes such as *stcM*, *cmlA*, *bla*_{TEM}, and *qnrC*. The superbug resistance gene *bla*_{NDM-1} was also found in about 10% of the isolates [32]. Studies have also illustrated colistin-resistant *E. coli* and *K. pneumoniae* carrying *mcr-1* on transferrable plasmids in poultry [33]. A review carried out by [34] found that a lot of chickens had ESBL-producing genes like CTX-M, TEM, SHV, OXA, *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, and *bla*_{TEM-1}. The most common gene among these was *bla*_{CTX-M}.

MECHANISMS OF RESISTANCE GENE TRANSFER

Many antibiotics are substances that occur naturally, leading co-resident bacteria to develop various strategies to evade their effects and ensure their survival. These organisms are frequently regarded as "intrinsically" resistant to antibiotics [35]. Nevertheless, in examining the paradox of antimicrobial resistance, the focus is not on microorganisms with inherent resistance traits, but instead on those that have developed resistance through acquisition, specifically organisms that were initially susceptible to antibiotics [36].

There are several ways that microorganisms can acquire resistance genes. It's important to note that antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) found in clinical pathogens are not the only ones that matter. All pathogenic, commensal, and environmental bacteria, as well as mobile genetic elements and bacteriophages, make up the resistome, which is a collection of ARGs that pathogenic bacteria can use to become resistant through horizontal gene transfer (HGT). HGT has caused antibiotic resistance to spread from commensal and environmental species to pathogenic and one of the major mechanisms of HGT is conjugation, followed by transformation and transduction [37,38].

CONJUGATION: Bacterial conjugation, also referred to as bacterial sex, is an essential method of horizontal gene transfer that facilitates the direct transfer of DNA from a donor bacterium to a receiver bacterium [39]. Integrative conjugative elements in chromosomes or genes on autonomously replicating plasmids encode the conjugative machinery, which facilitates the process of conjugation [40].

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

Fig. 1 shows a schematic representation of the process. Conjugation is often considered the most likely mechanism for the transfer of ARG. This is due to the fact that it provides better protection from the surrounding environment and a more efficient means of entering the host cell [38].

On a global scale, the IncK plasmid, denoted pCT, spread the *bla*_{CTX-M-14} gene to animals and humans across multiple continents via conjugation [41]. Experimental demonstrations on conjugation by [42] using broth mating and equal volumes of donor and recipient strains to mimic the conditions in the gastrointestinal tract of broilers showed that *E. coli* ESBL10682/*E. coli* IMT 20751/402, *E. coli* ESBL10682/*Serratia marcescens* subsp. *marcescens* DSM 30122, and *E. coli* ESBL10682/*S. enterica* serovar *Typhimurium* L1219-R32 were able to form transconjugants after a short period of incubation. They also demonstrated that 92% of their *Shigella* and 100% of the *Salmonella* isolates transferred resistant genes against tetracycline, ampicillin, chloramphenicol, and streptomycin to a recipient *E. coli* [43]. Another study conducted by [44] illustrated that the IncFIB/IncHI1B plasmid that confers resistance to azithromycin recovered from the *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strain could be efficiently disseminated to *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella*, and Gram-negative bacterial pathogens through conjugation. Other studies also indicated that *bla*_{CMY-2}-carrying plasmids are capable of conjugative transfer between

different poultry-associated bacterial genera under conditions relevant to broiler production [45].

TRANSFORMATION: It is defined as the process by which foreign DNA molecules are taken in by the cell wall and either stabilised and incorporated into the recipient genome or replicated as separate plasmids [37], allowing the recipient bacteria to acquire new traits such as antimicrobial-resistant genes [46]. These foreign DNAs are found free in the environment due to the death or lysis of another bacterium [41]. Fig. 1 shows a schematic representation of the process. Studies have demonstrated that cefotaxime and gentamicin resistance can be disseminated via transformation as well as the *bla*_{CTX-M-1}, *su*2 and *tet*(A) gene in diseased broilers [47, 48].

TRANSDUCTION: In transduction, a bacteriophage transmits new characteristics to the recipient bacterium by transferring chromosomal and extrachromosomal DNA from the donor bacterium. [49]. Transduction by bacteriophages is one of many horizontal gene transfer mechanisms, and recent findings have shown phage-mediated transduction to be a significant contributor to the dissemination of antibiotic resistance genes [49]. In an in vitro study conducted by [50] they demonstrated the process of transduction using phages from migratory birds. The *qnrA*, *tetB*, *bla*_{TEM}, and *sul*III genes were successfully transduced to *E. coli* isolates from poultry.

Fig1: Schematic presentation of resistant gene transfer adapted from [41]

PATTERNS OF RESISTANCE GENE TRANSFER

Some studies suggest that certain anthropogenic factors, including the excessive use of antibiotics for prophylaxis,

metaphylaxis, and bird fattening, significantly contribute to the proliferation of antimicrobial resistant genes (ARGs) in poultry, their environment, and among poultry workers[51].

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

Figure 2 schematically demonstrates the transfer of resistance genes among various species and organisms. The presence of antibiotic residues in poultry products, whether used for treating infections or promoting growth, generates waste that contains antibiotic-resistant bacteria. This contamination of the environment perpetuates the population of resistant bacteria and facilitates the transfer of genetic elements, such as resistance genes, across organisms. The utilization of goods like sanitizers, disinfectants, essential oils, and acetic acid can influence bacterial resistance, hence facilitating the dissemination of resistant bacteria and associated genes. Humans become infected with these resistant bacteria through the consumption of chicken or its products, contact with poultry litter, or association with other exposed animals [51, 52].

In the agricultural sector, specifically poultry farming, the extensive use of antibiotics for promoting growth and preventing disease greatly contributes to the rise of resistant

strains [53] that are transmitted through food supply chains, thereby posing health risks to humans when contaminated chicken products are consumed [54]. Studies have shown that agricultural runoff contaminates water sources and soil with antibiotic residues, promote the spread of antimicrobial resistance genes (ARGs) among environmental bacteria [55]. In several nations, especially in the Africa antibiotics are extensively utilised in livestock for treating and preventing infections, as well as for promoting growth in food animals [56]. A major concern has been that repeatedly exposing these animals to small doses of antibiotics contributes significantly to antimicrobial resistance [57]. Studies have indicated that antibiotics administered at sub-therapeutic levels frequently lead to the emergence and selection of resistant bacteria, which can be transmitted to humans through the food supply chain, direct animal contact, or environmental contamination[58-60]

Fig.2 : Transmission routes of antimicrobial-resistant bacteria and antimicrobial resistance genes in a poultry industry. Source [51]

FACTORS INFLUENCING RESISTANCE GENE ACQUISITION:

Acquisition of resistance genes is kind of described as survival of the fittest by the organisms and is either due to the selective pressure of the antibiotics and/or environmental factors [61]. Undoubtedly, antibiotics play a major role in the selection of bacterial resistance, but the spread of resistance genes and microorganisms in the environment greatly exacerbates the problem [62]. Anthropogenic sources continuously expose the environment to a wide variety of pollutants, potentially promoting horizontal gene transfer [63]. Antibiotic residues can be found in the environment for a considerable amount of time after treatment, and resistant

forms may select during or after antimicrobial therapy. In addition to antibiotics, the use of other agents, such as surface disinfectants, which have antibacterial properties in many households and are aimed at eliminating germs, also infiltrates the soil [61]. Human activities and the environment play a pivotal role in the acquisition and transfer of resistant genes [60]. The diagram below shows us how biocides, antibiotics, feed additives, and disinfectants can promote the acquisition of resistant organisms.

Fig 3: Schematic representation of anthropogenic factors that promote acquisition of resistant genes.

Source:[60]

FEED (ANTIBIOTIC AND HEAVY METALS): Antibiotics are used for treatment at appropriate doses. Nevertheless, the application of sublethal doses for prevention and growth promotions in poultry subjects these doses to pathogenic, commensal, and surrounding microorganisms upon excretion. Both pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacteria acquire resistance as a result of antibiotic selective pressure [63]. The resistant bacteria and their resistance genes will spread horizontally between the birds, the environment, and humans, thus posing a serious threat to human health [60]. Feces and urine excrete resistant bacteria into the environment, even those used for therapeutic purposes [65].

In addition to the use and misuse of antibiotics, the presence of heavy metals in the environment, such as copper, zinc, and mercury, exacerbates the acquisition and spread of resistance genes [64,65]. Evidence suggests that prolonged exposure to sub-MIC concentrations of certain metals raises the frequency of bacterial resistance to antibiotics through genetic modifications [68]. This discovery indicates that the lowered metal concentrations in numerous natural habitats exert a pervasive selective pressure on bacteria, potentially accelerating the development, acquisition, and dissemination of resistant strains. Data indicate a significant correlation between heavy metal resistance genes and antibiotic and disinfectant resistance genes in foodborne *Salmonella* [66].

DISINFECTANT AND BIOCIDES: Biocides are chemicals that are used to kill pathogenic microorganisms. They include disinfectants and preservatives, fungicides, algacides, rodenticides and insecticides, phages, and other biological agents [60]. A biocidal concentration that doesn't kill the target bacteria will cause a stress response, regardless

of the application method, leading to mechanisms that enable bacterial survival [67]. According to a review by [68] using biocides too much could make bacteria more resistant to them and also render them resistant to other types of antibiotics, even chemotherapeutic antibiotics. In an experiment conducted by [69], they showed that microorganisms in the environment were more likely to get resistant genes when they were exposed to biocides. This was true even though the organism used in the experiment didn't show any phenotypic or genotypic changes after being exposed to biocides, heavy metals, and antibiotics for 30 days. The findings indicated that prolonged exposure and other environmental factors play a vital role in the acquisition of resistance genes. Therefore, a higher level of bacterial resistance may result from improper disinfection of poultry farms [70]. Some Enterobacteriaceae, like *Klebsiella spp.*, *E. coli*, and *Salmonella spp.*, can get resistant genes and become more resistant when they are exposed to biocides [71].

ARTHROPODS: Arthropods, such as flies, blowflies, beetles, cockroaches, etc., are common in poultry farms and have been shown to carry multidrug-resistant bacteria identical to those found in poultry manure [72]. Several studies have indicated that insects can spread bacteria and resistance genes from one species to another in their digestive tracts [73,74]. Studies indicate, that flies, due to their close association with people and animals, pose a major public health risk. They carry bacterial pathogens on their body surfaces and in their alimentary tract, and they can transmit infections to humans through direct pathogen transfer or regurgitation and defecation [75].

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

In a study conducted by [76] they trapped 493 flies from various locations such as a dairy unit, a dog kennel, a poultry farm, a beef cattle unit, an urban trash facility, and an urban downtown area to isolate *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Staphylococcus spp.* In total, 35.3% of the flies were found to harbour antimicrobial-resistant bacteria, and 9.0% contained multidrug-resistant isolates. Three types of *E. coli* bacteria carrying extended-spectrum beta-lactamase (ESBL) and one type of *K. pneumoniae* bacteria carrying ESBL were found in houseflies. Whole-genome sequencing identified the antimicrobial resistance genes *bla_{CMY-2}* and *bla_{CTXM-1}* as ESBLs; these imply that flies not only carry antimicrobial-resistant bacteria but that their intestines provide a suitable environment for horizontal transfer of antimicrobial resistance genes [77].

BIOFILM FORMATION: Bacterial biofilms are often defined as communities of surface-attached bacteria which might facilitate the acquisition of antibiotic resistance genes [78]. Environmental conditions are known to be pivotal for facilitating biofilm formation, the development of antibiotic resistance mediated by biofilms, and their dissemination. Numerous studies have shown that environmental biofilms serve as hubs for the spread of antibiotic resistance genes (ARGs) [79]. In a study carried out by [80] all biofilm-producing *E. coli* isolates from chicken meat harboured the *bla_{TEM-1}* gene, which is an indication of resistance. Also, resistant genes on biofilms can be transmitted via horizontal gene transfer on mobile genetic elements [81].

POULTRY AMR ENTEROBACTERIACEAS AND IMPLICATIONS TO PUBLIC HEALTH

Poultry continues to be a significant reservoir for zoonotic multidrug-resistant organisms. The worldwide increase in antibiotic resistance among Gram-negative bacteria is a significant problem and necessitates enhanced surveillance [82]. Globally, over 60% of all produced antibiotics are utilised in animal production for therapeutic and non-therapeutic purposes. Poultry products rank among the most widely consumed globally. However, the extensive use of essential antibiotics in poultry production across various countries poses risks to product safety due to antimicrobial residues and enhances the likelihood of microbial resistance development and dissemination in poultry environments [83]. AMR presents a significant challenge for modern medicine and public health, as microorganisms evolve to resist the effects of antimicrobial agents, making previously effective treatments insufficient [84]. AMR leads to higher rates of illness, death, and healthcare expenses, accounting for nearly 700,000 fatalities globally each year, with projections suggesting that those numbers could rise to as many as 10 million deaths annually by 2050. In 2014, WHO identified AMR as one of the top ten global health threats, a status that remains unchanged nearly a decade later. The emergence and spread of AMR are accelerated by the misuse of antimicrobial agents (in agricultural, veterinary, and human health sectors),

inadequate infection control measures, poor sanitation, and improper food handling [85,86]. At its core, AMR is driven by genetic modifications within microbial populations, allowing them to survive and multiply despite the presence of antimicrobial drugs [87].

Enterobacteriaceae stands out due to its increasing resistance to multiple antibiotic classes. The emergence and spread of Enterobacteriaceae resistant genes have significant implications for public health, posing a substantial threat to global health security. The rapid dissemination of these genes has led to increased mortality rates, prolonged hospital stays, and escalated healthcare costs [88-90]. The presence of resistant genes, such as *bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{NDM}*, and *bla_{KPC}*, in Enterobacteriaceae has rendered many antimicrobials ineffective, limiting treatment options for severe infections [91-93]. The emergence of multi-drug-resistant strains of Enterobacteriaceae complicates standard treatment protocols. Patients with infections from these organisms may require treatment regimens that involve the use of last-resort antibiotics, which can have significant side effects and may not always be effective [4,91,94,].

Due to prolonged hospital stays, chronic illnesses deplete the resources of both the patient and the healthcare system. Economic productivity is also impacted by longer recovery times, which provide more quality time off. In a similar vein, AMR infections need further isolation measures, laboratory testing, and outpatient clinic visits [95]. Over a million lives are lost each year due to mortality directly caused by AMR infections [85]. The restricted ability to control infections might make basic procedures like surgery, organ transplants, chemotherapy, and neonatal care significantly riskier in the absence of effective antibiotics [96]. The economic burden associated with treating resistant infections has been estimated to reach billions of dollars annually in developed countries alone [4].

The AMR makes it possible for resistant zoonotic infections to spread from animal to human, endangering both human health and the food supply [97]. Antibiotic reservoirs of resistance have been sparked by the overuse of antibiotics in poultry to treat disease and encourage growth. This makes it easier for MDR Enterobacteriaceae to spread through the food chain or through handling animals such as poultry [98]. Furthermore, limited treatment options for animal diseases brought on by resistance encourage the spread of outbreaks among sheep, cattle, and poultry, requiring culling and causing large financial losses while endangering food supply [99]. According to estimates, livestock alone could cost \$3–4 billion in the upcoming decades due to AMR [4].

Enterobacteriaceae are not only significant in human health and animal health, they also pose risks in the agricultural sector. The use of antibiotics in agriculture contributes to the development of resistant bacteria in food-producing animals, which can then be transmitted to humans through the food chain [28]. The environment serves as a reservoir for resistant Enterobacteriaceae, complicating control efforts. Wastewater

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

and agricultural runoff are significant contributors to the spread of resistant strains, which can contaminate water supplies and soil, thereby affecting humans and animals alike [100].

CONSEQUENCES OF RESISTANT ENTEROBACTERIACEAE TO HUMAN HEALTH, HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS, AND SOCIETY

The overreliance on antibiotics has led to the emergence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, commonly referred to as superbugs, which present considerable challenges to treatment efficacy and can result in life-threatening infections [4]. Infections such as pneumonia, urinary tract infections, and bloodstream infections which were easily treated with standard antibiotics are becoming harder to manage, resulting in extended periods of illness and greater likelihood of complications [101]. Prolonged illnesses exhaust both individual and healthcare system resources as a result of extended hospitalisations. Extended recoveries adversely affect economic productivity by increasing time away from work [4].

Resistant Enterobacteriaceae complicates the treatment of chronic illnesses and medical procedures. Patients receiving chemotherapy, organ transplants, or major surgeries are at a heightened risk of contracting resistant infections due to their compromised immune systems [102,103]. In surgical environments, antibiotic prophylaxis is employed to prevent surgical site infections (SSIs), but rising AMR increases the threat of SSIs caused by resistant organisms, resulting in poorer patient outcomes such as prolong hospitalisations, extended durations of antibiotic therapy, higher rates of surgical revision and mortality [104].

Longer hospital stays, higher treatment costs for people with resistant Enterobacteriaceae infections, and the need for intensive care are the main things that cost healthcare systems a lot of money [105]. In the United States, the annual expenditure for treating AMR infections has doubled since 2002, amounting to USD 2.2 billion per year (approximately \$20,000 per patient) [5]. AMR infections lead to increased mortality rates, with odds ratios of 1.844 (95% CI: 1.187–2.865), and also result in higher rates of readmission. According to reports by [106], Africa needs about 6 billion dollars annually for an effective AMR response, and current funding is just a tenth of the amount allocated to other major diseases. This underfunding makes AMR a significant barrier to sustainable development, hindering progress towards sustainable development goals and the African Union's Agenda 2063.

The CDC reports estimates that by 2050 global healthcare expenditures may surpass USD 1 trillion yearly, and animal productivity may decrease by 2.6% to 7.5% each year due to antimicrobial resistance (AMR). In Africa, the situation is notably concerning, with 37 countries indicating the presence of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) in livestock, but merely 16% of African nations are implementing regular AMR

surveillance in animals as of 2023[106]. In addition to direct healthcare expenses, AMR imposes broader economic effects on society, primarily related to productivity losses arising from extended illness or premature death [103].

The pharmaceutical industry is also significantly affected by AMR. The expensive nature of developing new antibiotics, coupled with the relatively brief period of effectiveness before resistance develops, has caused a decline in funding for antibiotic research and development [1]. Leading to a decreasing pipeline of new antimicrobial options, worsening the AMR crisis due to lack of interest in investing in new antibiotics by pharmaceutical companies [101]. The high costs associated with clinical trials and the intricate regulatory landscape further deterred companies from engaging in antibiotic development. Although governments and health agencies have attempted to encourage renewed investment in antibiotic development, the financial support remains inadequate [107]

ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE AND TREATMENT CHALLENGES FOR ENTEROBACTERIACEAE

Addressing the emergence of antimicrobial resistance involves intricate challenges that lack straightforward solutions. The economics of food animal production and the pervasive incorporation of antimicrobials into medical practices hinder efforts to reduce their extensive use [108]. AMR has escalated to a critical global health challenge, jeopardising the effectiveness of existing treatment regimens for infectious diseases [109]. The emergence of AMR can be traced to various factors, including over-prescription of antibiotics, improper use of antimicrobials in agriculture, and poor infection prevention and control practices [4,110]. An important part of the problem comes from people in healthcare, patients, and agriculture misusing antibiotics. This creates selective pressure that helps resistant strains stay alive [83,111]. Furthermore, the lack of novel antimicrobial agents in the drug-development pipeline exacerbates the situation [4].

One of the primary challenges is the limited availability of effective treatment options for infections caused by resistant organisms, such as Enterobacteriaceae resulting in the use of last-resort antibiotics, which can have severe side effects [101]. For instance, infections caused by carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae (CRE) are notoriously difficult to manage [94]. Also, the treatment of Enterobacteriaceae infections is further complicated by the presence of multidrug-resistant genes, such as *bla_{CTX-M}*, *bla_{NDM}*, and *bla_{KPC}*, which confer resistance to multiple antimicrobials [112]. Horizontal gene transfer has made it easier for these genes to spread, which shows how important it is to control infections and responsibly use antibiotics [113].

A significant challenge in managing resistant infections lies in the necessity for prompt and precise diagnosis. Identifying the specific pathogen and its resistance characteristics is crucial for selecting the right treatment. Current diagnostic

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

strategies, mainly culture-based, can be lengthy and often lead to inappropriate antibiotic prescriptions [91]

STRATEGIES FOR CONTROLLING RESISTANCE GENE TRANSFER AND ANTIMICROBIAL RESISTANCE

Strategies to mitigate the spread of resistant genes and AMR are critical for preserving the effectiveness of current antibiotic therapies and safeguarding public health. It presents a formidable public health challenge that necessitates immediate and coordinated action across multiple fronts. A multi-faceted approach that involves surveillance, stewardship, infection control, alternative treatments, biotechnological innovations, and public health initiatives is vital [35]. Collaborative efforts among healthcare professionals, researchers, policymakers, poultry farmers and the public can significantly curb the rise of AMR and preserve the effectiveness of existing antibiotics. As the landscape of microbial resistance continues to evolve, ongoing research and adaptation strategies will be essential for sustaining global health, and this makes the adoption of a One Health approach, which recognises the interconnectedness of human, animal, and environmental health, an effective measure to control resistant gene transfer and mitigate the threat of AMR. [2,114,115]

To combat the rising threat of AMR, robust infection prevention and control (IPC) measures in healthcare settings are essential. These include rigorous hygiene protocols, appropriate use of personal protective equipment, and the implementation of antibiotic stewardship programs [116]. Antibiotic stewardship promotes the appropriate use of antibiotics by optimising their selection, dosage, and duration, thereby minimising resistance development [117]. Studies have indicated that effective stewardship can reduce antibiotic consumption and the incidence of resistant infections significantly [118].

Raising awareness about AMR among healthcare professionals, farmers, and the public is crucial for fostering responsible antibiotic use. Education initiatives can promote understanding of the implications of AMR and the importance of adhering to prescribed treatment regimens. Engaging healthcare providers, patients, veterinarians, and farmers in conversations about the risks associated with antibiotic overuse and misuse can significantly enhance compliance with stewardship guidelines

Surveillance plays a crucial role in understanding the dynamics of AMR. Continuous monitoring of antibiotic usage and resistance patterns enables healthcare systems to develop targeted strategies to address AMR challenges [90]. Moreover, investing in research for new antimicrobial agents and alternative therapies, such as phage therapy and vaccines, is vital in mitigating AMR impacts [91].

Phage therapy, which employs bacteriophages to target and kill specific bacteria, offers a potential alternative to traditional antibiotics [119]. This approach can be particularly

useful against multi-drug-resistant strains such as Enterobacteriaceae [120]. Also, looking into new antimicrobials, like antimicrobial peptides and targeted therapies, could lead to new ways to fight AMR [121]. The use of probiotics and prebiotics, organic acids, immunostimulants, bacteriocins, phytochemical feed additives, phytocides, nanoparticles and essential oils should also be encouraged in animal husbandry [99,122]

Fostering collaboration among various sectors by developing a more comprehensive approach to AMR can help curtail the problem of AMR. For example, the Global Antimicrobial Resistance Surveillance System (GLASS) provides a framework for countries to gather and share data on AMR [85]. Another example is the European Commission's (EC) 2006 decree prohibiting the use of antibiotics as growth promoters in feed [121]. Subsequent investigations revealed reduction in antibiotic resistance in areas prohibited from using antibiotics as growth promoters compared to those without such a policy [122].

The agricultural sector plays a significant role in the emergence and dissemination of AMR. Reducing the non-therapeutic use of antibiotics in livestock for growth promotion and disease prevention is critical [96,123,124]. Promoting the use of alternative methods, like better animal care and biosecurity measures, can lower the need for antibiotics and stop the spread of genes that are resistant to the food chain [97,108]. Food Safety Practices and Proper Hygiene ensuring proper cooking and handling of poultry products can mitigate the risk of transmitting resistant bacteria to humans [123,125].

Over-the-Counter (OTC) oral and injectable antibiotic sales and dispensing, which is still popular in many developing nations, should be strictly regulated. A doctor or veterinarian must prescribe antibiotics. Patient and pharmacy drug dispenser awareness programs on antibiotics and AMR are advised, as is reevaluating antibiotic policies based on local and regional AMR monitoring data [90]

The spread of antimicrobial resistance and the transfer of resistant genes represent a multifaceted challenge that requires a comprehensive approach. By implementing effective surveillance systems, promoting antibiotic stewardship, enhancing infection control measures, exploring alternative treatments, and reducing agricultural antibiotic use, the global community can significantly mitigate the impact of AMR. Addressing this issue will require collaboration among healthcare providers, veterinarians, farmers, researchers, policymakers, and the public to safeguard the effectiveness of antibiotics for future generations.

CONCLUSION

Several antimicrobial resistance genes have been found in poultry, its products, and its environment. These genes can be passed on to humans and cause serious health problems. To combat the spread of antibiotic resistance effectively, it is

Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

essential for stakeholders, including governments and farmers, to implement and enforce policies to curb the spread of antimicrobial resistance. This includes prioritising drug withdrawal periods for the use of antibiotics in poultry farming and ensuring proper hygiene and biosecurity measures are in place. Education and awareness campaigns can also play a crucial role in informing farmers and consumers about the risks associated with antimicrobial resistance. By adopting these strategies, stakeholders can help protect public health and reduce the prevalence of resistant strains in both animals and humans. Moreover, continuous monitoring and identification of antibiotic-resistant bacteria in the poultry industry is crucial. Implementing these measures can help protect human health and address the growing concern of antimicrobial resistance.

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Poultry as Hidden Reservoirs: The Growing Public Health Threat of Resistant Enterobacteriaceae

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